

2022

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/peecrp:1070589>

A Comparative Analysis of Generation Z with the Greatest Generation through Psychological Traumas

Juraev Shakhboz Akbarovich

Immanuel Kant Baltic Federal University,

shakhbozjuraev17@gmail.com

orcid: 0000-0003-3360-4655

Abstract

The rising cases of nationalism, right-wing populism, and neo-Nazism in several communities resemble the ideological void in the growing generation's psychology through traumatic events. As long as the increase of radicalization threatens for stability and peace of societies, the rationale research of deep roots of crisis-events remain in the broad spectrum of political and social studies. The objective of the work is to shed light on several aspects of this tendency by comparing the two generational layers. In the paper, the method of historical-comparative analysis is used by selecting and juxtaposing psychological traumatic discourses. The research concludes that the negative influences of the traumas should be mitigated by reforms of schooling and education taking into account generation's psychological background.

Key words: psychological traumas, Generation Z, Greatest Generation, nationalism, right-wing populism

2022

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/peecrp:1070589>

Introduction

In dictionary of Merriam-Webster, Generation Z is defined as “people born in the late 1990s and early 2000s” and characterized as “tech-savvy, pragmatic, open-minded, individualistic but also socially responsible” (Merriam-Webster). Donald Trump may be the first U.S. president most Gen Zers know as they turn 18, and just as the contrast between George W. Bush and Barack Obama shaped the political debate for Millennials, the current political environment may have a similar effect on the attitudes and engagement of Gen Z, though how remains a question (Dimock, 2019). Generation Z is also expected to be ‘fortunate ones’ as sung by a famous rock group Linking Park. However, the several turning-points occurred around the globe at the beginning of XXI century have, potentially, influenced the mainstream of events. Notably, white supremacists in the US are possible to inherit their ideologies to their descendants.

In his research, Vieten (2020) writes that “xenophobia can be mobilised in times of crises, for example, in the bank liquidity crisis of 2008, as a symptom of ”capitalism in crisis”; in the run up to the Brexit referendum in 2016, when rhetorically immigration was linked to the social welfare crisis; or in the context of the economic, social, and ecological global public health crisis epitomised in the 2020 virus pandemic.” Rawi Abdelal (2020) argues that “high-income earners can isolate themselves at home, continue to work, and also have almost everything they need delivered by the working poor. Those thrust into isolated unemployment without income and limited support will endure other potential crises unrelated to exposure to the novel coronavirus: substance abuse, domestic violence, mental health disorders, and other, less novel ways to get sick or die. Thus the emergent

2022

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/peecrp:1070589>

backlash against quarantine policies is reproducing some of the same politics that already represented years of frustration with the economy and its management by political and business elites.” In fact, a rationale psychological approach to traumatic disorders of the Generation Z remains an integral part of political, economic and educational reforms in order to avoid negative results of radical ideas as in pre-World War period.

Research methodology

In the work, comparative method of analysis comes to the fore of the research by selecting traumatic events from the history of Greatest Generation and Generation Z and juxtaposing the discourses that shaped or have been shaping the psychology of the cohorts. The method by its means shows the mainstream of a trend, which is likely to lead to a similar or close results with another tendency or event in history. Comparative analysis is a methodology within political science that is often used in the study of political systems, institutions or processes. This can be done across a local, regional, national and international scale. Further, Comparative analysis is grounded upon empirical evidence gathered from the recording and classification of real-life political phenomena. Where-by other political studies develop policy via ideological and/or theoretical discourse, comparative research aims to develop greater political understanding through a scientifically constrained methodology (Stafford, 2013).

Accordingly, in the article, Greatest Generation or World War generation is selected in the paper as a role model of Generation Z considering the closeness of psychological traumatic history.

A Brief History of World War Generation

2022

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/peecrp:1070589>

In 1925, Adolf Hitler, the leader of Nazi Party and future chancellor in Germany, published his manifesto ‘Mein Kampf’ (List of 1925 Major News Events in History, n.d.), a book composed of thesis statements for Nazis ideology. In particular, ‘this year also signifies the birth of the youngest (latest) members of a cohort, Greatest Generation (Kagan, 2021)’ (G.I. Generation, World War generation) who are the main participants of the World War II. The behavioral background of the cohort had been shaped by several political, social, military and economic crisis and influenced to their future moral and spirituality.

Firstly, the older members of the generation (born in 1901) faced World War I in their early ages. In spite of the fact that their fathers and grandfathers, not they themselves, had fought in the military operations, economic difficulties, social instability, loss of a family member caused a psychological trauma to appear. In fact, children had grown up under the fear of war since their school ages, seeing real consequences in their family and neighbors.

The second traumatic event for the generation’s behavior was defined as the Great Depression from 1929 to 1933. When they were ready to join workforce (the oldest was 28 and the youngest were 4 years old), economic instability began in the world. As a result, job opportunities had decreased, currencies had devaluated, children had left schools to support family, and labor had depreciated.

The two global turbulences, such as fear, unemployment and financial difficulties led to psychological traumas in G.I. Generation’s morality. Consequently, the parties, which had been propagating populism at the beginning of 1920s, sparked historical revanchist, nationalist, racist and fascist ideologies. The morally-broken cohort of the society supported these political parties. In the end, emotionally

2022

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/peecrp:1070589>

desperate and discouraged people followed radical ideas in the 1930s and at the first part of 1940s.

Early Years of the XXI Century

A little boy, at his age of 4, was playing a Tekken Tag Tournament in Play Station 2. He and his peers were expected to live in a peace, stable and liberal world due to technological development occurred in digital sphere at the last decades of the XX century. However, on September 11, 2001, two planes crashed into twin towers has ended Fukuyama's liberal world order. The young Zoomers began to live under the threat of terrorism. Some governments rose taxes to provide army warring against armed groups in Afghanistan or the Middle East countries. It symbolizes the first trauma for Generation Z.

Secondly, in September 2008, a financial model that is described as 'too big to fail' has failed as a result of mortgage crisis. This chain of bankruptcy caused a global economic recession and decreased family incomes. 'According to reports, real gross domestic product (GDP) fell some 4.3% from a high in fourth-quarter 2007 to its low in second-quarter 2009 - and, to boot, the unemployment rate skyrocketed from 5% in 2007 to 10% in October of 2009 (Sraders, 2019).' The 11-years-old or younger children had to attend to lower-quality schools while in some countries, where the government subsidize schools, the average number of pupils per class had been increased. In terms of high education, students had either left their universities and colleges or assumed a long-term debt. The shortage in family income in the developing countries led to a grow in underage work involvement among boys and marriage among girls. It was the second time that the Zoomers' psychology got traumatized under the strain of global crisis.

2022

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/peecrp:1070589>

Finally, the real depression-like downturn came onto the stage with the coronavirus pandemic. The lockdown of state-borders hit the global economy hard and put the future of new generation under the question. The oldest Zoomer has turned out 23, at which age they are ready to enter job market. It is the high time for the youth to find a way in their life and begin their careers, however, most companies have closed their doors for entry level job seekers. ‘These are difficult times to be a young person, making your way in the world. Internships that might have led to paying work have largely evaporated; those that remain are as prized as a rare pearl. A report from the Sutton Trust in July found that 61% of employers surveyed have cancelled all or some of the internships they’d usually offer, while 48% think there will be fewer such opportunities over the next year (Kale, 2020).’ – writes the Guardian.

All the traumas, the rise of extremism, the Great Recession and corona crisis have shaped the psychological condition of generation Z since their childhood. Most of the problems they are facing resemble those that Greatest generation once encountered. The threat of war, high unemployment rate, low incomes and depression enabled the rise of Fascism and Nazism to power in the 1920-30s.

Post-Covid Era Challenges

It is clear that the fascism had been defeated and militarism had been capitulated with the end of World War II. There is little chance of seizing governments by these ideologies in the modern world. Also, Zoomers’ destiny is apparent not to retaliate that of World War generation. Nevertheless, nationalism, racism and populism have remained and several trends have arisen to boost around the world: Misinterpretation of Islam after 09/11 and distorted operations of the US as white

2022

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/peecrp:1070589>

people's invasion into Afghanistan and Iraq radicalize various groups from both Islam and Western civilizations. Starting with Islamophobia (additionally with the migration crisis), several nationalistic and populist right-wing groups and political parties came to power or reached successful votes on elections in the United States and Europe by dictating “them and us” concept and arousing emotions of people.

The financial problems related to the recession have influenced education quality and payment status of Zoomers. However, many of them were at schools, colleges and universities during the crisis. As an illustration of the US, ‘declines in state support are closely correlated with increases in tuition across the country. States that were hardest hit by the recession and that cut appropriations to higher education the most also had the highest tuition increases. The worst-off states raised four-year tuition, on average, by \$2,800, while those least affected raised it by less than half that amount. At community colleges, tuition increased by \$680 in the worst-off states and by \$380 in those least affected by recession (Johnson, 2014).’

The populist governments are coming to power in the most of the countries during the second decade of the new century. This process is undergoing under the shadow of economic recovery. However, the populism has already an effect on more and more countries. ‘In Europe, the results of the 2014 European Parliament elections were largely interpreted as a populist backlash, giving rise to the success of Eurosceptic parties. At the domestic level, right-wing populist parties have garnered a parliamentary foothold – and in some cases governmental power – in countries across Western, Northern, and Eastern Europe (Bossetta & Husted,

2022

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/peecrp:1070589>

2017).’

Nationalism and racism have been strengthening due to the turbulence on political, economic and social spheres. ‘The global economic system has come into misbalance and, in Wallerstein’s view, structural contradictions and polarization have reached the point of bifurcation of the global system. He believes that the global capitalist system should be replaced by another political and economic system at about 2040, the outline of which is now yet unclear (Statkus, 2019).’

These trends along with psychological traumas play an important role in the life of Zoomers. The corona crisis and pandemic lockdown push individualism among this cohort of generation. Moreover, the unemployment and financial inadequacy spur the fight for limited resources. In that case, some nationalist and racist parties are possible to stress on their ideologies to escalate the process. Definitely, governments and organizations should prepare for avoiding from radicalization and polarization of interest groups in term of religion, nation, race and gender to occupy overly opportunities.

Conclusion

It is clear that the crises such as World War I and Great depression had a great influence on the psychology of Greatest generation, which were distorted by racist and nationalist movements in Italy, Germany and Spain. However, it is not the only consequences of those instabilities but also the fallacy of political, social, economic and educational institutions during the Roaring Twenties when adequate opportunities arisen to cure the traumatic void.

2022

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/>
рестр:1070589

Events in the early XXI century, including a war against terrorism without a clear definition, Great Recession and COVID-19 lockdown following with corona-crisis, hurt the national, religious, financial and psychological status of the Generation Z. History shows a clear sample of how psychological traumas of people, economic difficulties and social problems were manipulated by radical parties. To prevent the retaliation of the social instabilities generation Z may face, schooling, education and job opportunities should be rehabilitated by the time when discriminations are inflamed in some societies and communities.

References

- Abdelal, R. (28 May 2020 г.). Populism, the Pandemic, and the Crisis of Globalization. Получено из Valдай Discussion Club: <https://valdaiclub.com/a/highlights/populism-the-pandemic-and-the-crisis/>
- Bossetta, M., & Husted, E. (December 2017 г.). Introduction: Populism in the 21st Century: Critical reflections on a global phenomenon. Politik, стр. 1.
- Dimock, M. (17 January 2019 г.). Defining generations: Where Millennials end and Generation Z begins. Получено из Pew Research Center: <https://www.pewresearch.org/fact-tank/2019/01/17/where-millennials-end-and-generation-z-begins/>
- Johnson, N. (2014). College Costs, Prices and the Great Recession. Lumina Foundation.
- Kagan, J. (26 April 2021 г.). The Greatest Generation. Получено из Investopedia: https://www.investopedia.com/terms/t/the_greatest_generation.asp#:~:text=The%20Greatest%20Generation%20is%20a,book%20by%20the%20same%20name.
- Kale, S. (30 August 2020 г.). No internships, no entry-level work: under-25s fear

2022

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/peecrp:1070589>

Covid jobs squeeze. Получено из The Guardian: <https://www.theguardian.com/money/2020/aug/30/no-internships-no-entry-level-work-under-25s-fear-a-jobs-squeeze>

List of 1925 Major News Events in History. (б.д.). Получено из The people History: <https://www.thepeoplehistory.com/1925.html>

Merriam-Webster.

Sraders, A. (16 July 2019 г.). What Was the Great Recession? History, Causes and Consequences. Получено из The Street: <https://www.thestreet.com/politics/what-was-the-great-recession-14664025>

Stafford, A. (14 November 2013 г.). Comparative Analysis Within Political Science. Получено из E-International Relations: <https://www.e-ir.info/2013/11/14/the-value-of-comparative-analysis-within-political-science/>

Statkus, N. (2019). The Role of Nationalism in the 21st Century System of International Relations. Lithuanian Annual Strategic Review, стр. 142.

Vieten, U. M. (2020). The “New Normal” and “Pandemic Populism”: The COVID-19 Crisis and Anti-Hygienic Mobilisation of the Far-Right. Social Science, 6.

